

CHEMICAL-TOXICOLOGICAL STUDY OF BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE ADDITIVES**Obloqulov J.B.**
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Relevance. In the last decade, the demand for biologically active additives has been growing sharply. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 30–35% of the world's population regularly uses various dietary supplements. In the USA, this figure is more than 50%, and in Japan - about 60%. According to statistics from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022, the number of registered biologically active additives was more than 1,200. At the same time, the presence of illegally imported or uncertified additives on the market has been noted. Along with the widespread use of BFAs, the issue of their safety is also relevant. The hidden addition of pharmacologically active substances or exceeding the norm of heavy metal ions in some additives poses a serious threat to human health.

Research objective: To determine the chemical and toxicological composition of biologically active additives, to illustrate their hazardous components through examples, and to analyze modern analytical methods.

Methods and methodology. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) – determination of plant alkaloids, flavonoids, vitamins and amino acids.

- Gas-liquid chromatography (GC-MS) – identification of volatile or thermostable substances such as ephedrine, sibutramine, yohimbine, caffeine.

- Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) – assessment of the amount of heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Hg, As) in supplements.

- Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) – determination of toxic elements at ultra-low concentrations.

- Bioassays – assessment of toxic effects in cell culture or animal models.

Results. Studies show that the risks of biologically active supplements are concentrated in three main areas: 1. Hidden addition of pharmacological substances: In 2018, inspections in China revealed sibutramine in 40% of weight loss supplements. According to the US FDA, between 2017 and 2022, more than 700 supplements were found to contain illegal additions of pharmacological substances, including sildenafil, phenolphthalein, and ephedrine derivatives. 2. Presence of heavy metals: A 2020 study in India found that 18% of 82 Ayurvedic supplements contained lead and cadmium above the permissible levels. In Uzbekistan, in 2023, some supplements sold as “herbal immunomodulators” were found to contain zinc (Zn) and lead (Pb) levels 2–3 times higher than the established hygienic standards. 3. Toxicity of plant alkaloids: Some plant-based supplements contain pyrrolizidine alkaloids, which have a toxic effect on the liver. In Germany, cases of hepatotoxic syndrome were reported in patients who consumed these types of supplements in 2015. To strengthen the chemical-toxicological control system: Introduce modern analytical methods such as LC-MS/MS and ICP-MS into the certification process of PFAS in Uzbekistan.

- Conduct regular laboratory control of products placed on the market.

It is necessary to establish strict monitoring of illegal trade and online sales.

Conclusion. Although the consumption of biologically active additives is expanding worldwide, the presence of components that pose a health risk has been confirmed in many studies.

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Heavy metals and pharmacological substances have also been detected in some additives on the Uzbek market. It is important to strengthen the chemical and toxicological control of BPA, introduce international experience, and raise consumer awareness.